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Validation of Blade Element Momentum & Free Vortex Wake Methods with Water Tunnel Data for a Scaled Marine Turbine Rotor

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Abstract

Blade Element Momentum (BEM) and Free Vortex Wake (FVW) methods play a pivotal role in the design and analysis of wind and marine hydrokinetic turbine technologies, including assessment of load response, power performance, cavitation potential and wake flow recovery. Initial validation results are presented herein for well-established BEM model, OpenFAST, using experimental data obtained from water tunnel tests conducted on a 1:8.7 scale-model of the US Department of Energy's marine hydrokinetic family 1 (MHKF1) reference turbine rotor. Both models accurately reproduce measured power performance coefficients with respect to tip-speed-ratio (TSR) and resolve the main features of the near-wake field. However, more extensive validation of these important models is needed through comparison with measured blade loads.

Keywords: Hydrokinetic Turbine; Blade Element Momentum (BEM); Free Vortex Wake (FVW); Validation

1. Introduction

Model comparison and validation with experimental measurements to characterize and assess model performance is critically important to build confidence in model predicted results. . Our study goal is to validate two well-established BEM and FVW models, the Code for Axial and Crossflow TURbine Simulation (CACTUS) and OpenFAST. Both models have been validated for marine and wind turbine rotor applications, e.g., [2], but model validation has mainly been limited to comparison between predicted and measured power performance curves. Few validation studies for these models have evaluated their performance in predicting load response, cavitation potential or wake velocity profiles. Herein, OpenFAST is validated using power performance and cavitation measurements from water tunnel tests of a 1:8.7 scale model of the US Department of Energy's (USDOE) marine hydrokinetic (family 1 hydrofoils) MHKF1 reference marine turbine [1].

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2. Methods

2.1. Scale-Model MHKF1 Rotor

Experimental measurements for the present model validation study were collected for a 1:8.7 scale model of the USDOE MHKF1 reference turbine rotor tested at the Garfield Thomas Water Tunnel (GTWT) at the Applied Research Lab, Penn State University [1]. The experimental setup and scale model rotor are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the model rotor and dynamometer installed in the GTWT test section, and a photograph of the installed rotor [1].

2.2. CACTUS

CACTUS is an open-source blade element and free vortex wake (FVW) code developed by Sandia National Laboratories [2]. In this code, the turbine blades are discretized into blade elements, each associated with two-dimensional airfoil polar data stored in lookup tables. The Kutta-Joukowski theorem links lift data to boundary vorticity at each blade element, while the Helmholtz theorem recovers spanwise and trailing vorticities. The wake is represented using a potential flow model, employing straight-line vortex elements to simulate induced velocities based on the Biot-Savart law. CACTUS adopts a potential flow approach, disregarding viscous effects. Vortex filaments in the wake are advected by the freestream flow without dissipation or diffusion, though regularization is implemented by setting a cutoff radius for vortex cores [3].

2.3. OpenFAST

OpenFAST, is the National Renewable Energy Lab's (NREL's) open-source physics-based engineering model for whole-turbine simulation [4]. Comprising modular components, OpenFAST couples multiple independent modules. The AeroDyn module simulates rotor and tower aero/hydrodynamics, while the rotor wake and induction effects are modeled by applying quasi-steady or dynamic blade element momentum (BEM) theory, or a free vortex wake (FVW) formulation. The dynamic BEM model factors in time-varying wake and induction effects stemming from transient inflow or operating conditions. An FVW module known as cOnvecting Lagrangian Filaments (OLAF) employs a lifting-line representation of the blades, characterized by a distribution of bound circulation. This distribution generates free vorticity emitted into the wake. The OLAF model employs a Lagrangian approach, discretizing the turbine wake into Lagrangian markers [4], and diffusion can be modeled by the core-spreading method unlike CACTUS. Similar to CACTUS, lookup tables of two-dimensional airfoil polar data are employed to represent turbine blades.

2.4. Simulation Setup

Blade element models break down a blade into several small segments and then determine the forces on each of these small blade elements by using static airfoil data, including the lift force, drag force, and optional pitching moment and minimum pressure coefficients versus angle of attack (AoA). This data is usually obtained from experiments or 2-dimensional panel method codes like XFOIL [5]. For both CACTUS and OpenFAST blade element models in the present study, the blades of the MHKF1 turbine are discretized into 20 uniformly distributed elements. Each element utilizes distinct sets of airfoil polars, which are provided as lookup tables covering a range of Reynolds numbers and AoAs. These lookup table polars are generated by extrapolating XFOIL polar data from AoAs of -10 to 30° to cover

a range of -180° to 180° using the Viterna method. Within the models, required lift, drag, pitch moment and minimum pressure coefficients at specific AoA and Reynolds number combinations are obtained by interpolation. Fig. 2. Illustrates the airfoil coefficient curves at various AoAs and Reynolds number for the mid-span airfoil section (MHKF-240s airfoil) of the blade, estimated from XFOIL runs.

Fig. 2. Estimated curves of lift (top left), drag (top right), pitch moment (bottom left) and minimum pressure (bottom right) coefficients over a range of AoAs at various Reynolds numbers for the mid-span section of the blade (MHKF1-240s airfoil).

Fig. 3. 10 minutes power and thrust coefficients variation estimated from the simulation with and without turbulent inflow

In the present model, 0.3% turbulence intensity of the water tunnel experiment condition is ignored since it changes estimated power performance coefficient within 0.2% as show in Fig. 3.

3. Results

The results of the OpenFAST simulation using the dynamic BEM model are compared with experimental measurements of [1] in Fig. 4. While Fontaine et al. conducted blockage correction for power and thrust coefficients, the measured torque coefficients were not adjusted. Therefore, blockage corrected values for torque coefficients were estimated assuming the torque coefficient can be expressed as the power coefficient over the TSR. Comparison of the OpenFAST predicted power, torque, and thrust coefficients to measured values at the best operating point (BOP) of the MHKF1 rotor at a tip speed ratio = 4 indicate discrepancies of 4.5%, 5.7%, and -3.5%, respectively in the 5 m/s inflow speed. More pronounced discrepancies are generally observed at higher tip speed ratios, indicating potential limitations of the models to predict power performance under extreme operating conditions.

Fig. 4. Predicted coefficient curves of power (top left), thrust (top right), and torque (bottom left) obtained from OpenFAST simulations and blockage corrected measurement data of Fontaine et al. [1].

For inflow conditions of 3.0 ~ 5.0 m/s, Model underpredicts power coefficients at the best operating point (BOP) and at higher tip-speed-ratio (TSR), while the model overpredict thrust coefficient at the same range. Distinct discrepancies with measured data are observed in the power coefficient curves compared to thrust and torque coefficients, but are within 6% of measured values which is adequate for the purpose of design analysis. Notable Reynolds number dependency is observed from both OpenFAST simulation and the measurement in inflow speed of 2.0 m/s, while there is no significant impact of Reynolds number for $U = 3.0 \sim 5.0$ m/s. Model fails to capture the

Reynolds number dependency at lower TSR ($U = 2.0$ m/s) since local chord Reynolds number at large part of the blade in that condition are less than the Reynolds number range of the look up table polars. From the results of 7.0 m/s inflow condition, Model shows the limitation to predict turbine degradation due to cavitation breakdown at high inflow speed.

In addition to the coefficient curves, cavitation potential over the blades estimated from the OpenFAST simulation using the dynamic BEM model is compared with the experimental measurements of [1]. In the experiment, cavitation inception was assessed by reducing the tunnel pressure from 310 kPa until cavitation was observed visually on each blade, and then the pressure was raised until all visual signs of cavitation abated to assess cavitation desinence. OpenFAST simulations to assess performance predicting cavitation potential are performed at the BOP and the same 4 m/s inflow velocity condition as the scale-model cavitation test. Four different static pressures, 306, 202, 133 and 115 kPa, corresponding to tip vortex cavitation numbers, 38.7, 25.7, 17.0 and 14.8, are considered in the simulations to compare the results with Fontaine et al.'s cavitation tests. The test results are shown in Fig. 5. (a), a photograph of the intermittent tip vortex cavitation at the water tunnel static pressure of 306 kPa, and Fig. 5. (b) for steady tip-vortex cavitation at 202 kPa static pressure. Fig. 5. (c) and (d) are at the static pressure of 133 and 115 kPa when the blade cavitation inception near the cavitation breakdown point and the developed blade cavitation during cavitation breakdown were observed, respectively.

Fig. 5. Photographs of intermittent tip vortex cavitation (a), steady tip-vortex cavitation (b), blade cavitation inception near the cavitation breakdown point (c), and developed blade cavitation during cavitation breakdown (d) [1].

In the OpenFAST simulations, cavitation potential is predicted with the assumption that cavitation occurs when the local cavitation number is greater than or equal to the critical cavitation number. Fig. 6. illustrates local cavitation numbers calculated by the minimum pressure coefficient and critical cavitation numbers at the four different static pressure conditions along the blade. Cavitation numbers are only shown from the mid-span to the tip as cavitation is only observed near the blade tip. Fig. 5. shows that the model predicts no cavitation at the static pressure of 202 kPa for which the water tunnel experiment observed steady tip-vortex cavitation at the same pressure. This is not surprising as a dynamic BEM method cannot simulate blade tip-vortices. Nevertheless, the observed cavitation at water tunnel static pressures of 133 kPa or less is predicted by OpenFAST. The model predicts cavitation over about 25% of blade when the static pressure is reduced to 115 kPa.

Fig. 6. Estimated ratio of local cavitation number to critical cavitation number at four different static pressure conditions along the blade ($U=4.0\text{m/s}$, $\text{TSR}=3.91$). A ratio greater than one indicating the occurrence of cavitation.

4. Conclusions

The present study demonstrates that the OpenFAST BEM model's ability to predict power performance and cavitation, while not perfect, is still adequate for rotor design, analysis and performance assessment. It also shows model limitations under certain operating conditions. Preliminary results comparing OpenFAST predictions and measured power performance curves indicate this BEM model underpredict power and torque coefficients and overpredict thrust coefficient at the BOP and at higher TSR, but are within 6% of measured values which is adequate for the purpose of design analysis. Discrepancies are likely due to inaccurate estimates for the empirically derived coefficients generated by XFOIL at each of the 2D foil sections and could be addressed by deriving these coefficients experimentally or using a higher fidelity Unsteady Reynolds averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS). Even though the OpenFAST dynamic BEM model cannot predict tip-vortex cavitation, results herein demonstrate its ability to capture cavitation inception and breakdown. More comprehensive model validation is planned, including comparison of blade-load response, and wake velocity profiles for validating the FVW modules.

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